

EXAMINING THE IMPLEMENTATION OF THE POWER SYSTEM ANALYSIS IN SELECTED MANUFACTURING COMPANIES IN LAGUNA THROUGH THE KNOWLEDGE, ATTITUDE, AND PRACTICE FRAMEWORK

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ABSTRACT

Power System Analysis (PSA), which includes Short Circuit Analysis, Load Flow Calculations, Protection Coordination, and Arc Flash Studies, is significant in ensuring electrical safety and system reliability in industrial facilities. Recent mandates from DOLE and DPWH prompted companies to comply. However, many organizations still perform PSA mainly for documentation purposes, and the level of understanding and implementation varies. This study examined whether manufacturing companies in Laguna genuinely integrate PSA into their safety and reliability programs or perform it merely to meet regulatory requirements. Focusing on selected manufacturing companies in Calamba Premiere International Park, the study used the Knowledge-Attitude-Practice (KAP) framework. It examined the extent of PSA implementation, determined the knowledge, attitude, and practice of technical personnel toward PSA, and developed management directives to improve PSA implementation and strengthen electrical safety and reliability. Data were gathered through a researcher-developed survey questionnaire and observation checklist. Results revealed wide variations in PSA implementation, ranging from excellent to poor. Although respondents reported high knowledge and attitude scores, their actual practice was lower, particularly in advanced PSA components. This confirmed a clear gap between perceived understanding and actual implementation in the field. To address these gaps, the study developed management directives emphasizing the enhancement of technical competence, provision of appropriate software and tools, stronger organizational support, integration of PSA into preventive maintenance programs, and the need for regularly updated PSA studies. Continuous monitoring of PSA activities was also recommended to promote consistent,

proactive, and safety-oriented implementation, ultimately improving electrical system reliability in the manufacturing sector.

Keywords: *Power System Analysis, Electrical Safety and Reliability, Knowledge-Attitude-Practice Framework, Semiconductors and Microelectronics, Industrial Manufacturing, Engineering Management*

INTRODUCTION

Electrical safety and reliability remain one of the most critical concerns in the field of engineering. The National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) reported that from 2012 to 2016, approximately 36% of all fires involved electrical wiring and related equipment, while 50% to 60% of electrical fires in non-residential structures were linked to electrical distribution and lighting systems (Campbell, 2019). In the Philippines, the Bureau of Fire Protection recorded that 625 out of 2,307 fire incidents, or about 27%, were caused by electrical issues during the first two months of 2025 (Joviland, 2025). These statistics raise a significant concern: *Do industrial companies truly recognize the importance of electrical safety and reliability in operational effectiveness, or are they merely treated as regulatory obligations?*

Manufacturing industries rely heavily on efficient and reliable electrical systems to support their day-to-day operations. A single fault in the power system can lead to equipment damage, production downtime, financial losses, or threats to personnel safety. For this reason, electrical systems must be designed, maintained, and regularly assessed to prevent equipment failure, unplanned outages, and safety hazards.

One of the essential tools used in evaluating electrical systems is Power System Analysis (PSA). It is a set of engineering studies conducted to evaluate the performance, reliability, safety, and efficiency of an electrical system. PSA includes Short Circuit Analysis, Load Flow Calculation, Protection Coordination Studies, and Arc Flash Hazard Analysis and entails using electrical engineering simulations and calculations to evaluate power systems' performance, study, and understand their behavior, and make well-informed decisions about their control, operation, and design (Arunaachalam, 2023). In industrial facilities, PSA plays a vital role in ensuring proper equipment coordination, fault detection, and preventive maintenance, ultimately contributing to safer and more reliable electrical operations.

In the Philippines, regulatory agencies have mandated stricter compliance in the evaluation of electrical systems. According to the Department of Interior and Local Government (DILG) Memorandum Circular No. 2016-23, the Department of Public Works and Highways National Building Code Memorandum Circular No. 02 Series of 2015, and the Department of Labor and Employment requirements for the Certificate of Electrical Inspection, electrical design analysis is required prior to the installation, operation, or utilization of electrical systems. The Philippine Electrical Code (PEC) 2017 further specifies that the required design analysis must include voltage drop calculations, short

circuit analysis, protection coordination of overcurrent protective devices, and arc flash hazard analysis, collectively referred to as Power System Analysis (PSA).

Globally, PSA has long been regarded as a standard engineering practice in industries. However, despite its technical importance, PSA has not historically been widely implemented across industrial facilities in the country. With the recent mandates from DOLE and DPWH, manufacturing companies are increasingly required to comply with PSA documentation as part of regulatory and safety standards. Nevertheless, a gap remains between compliance and the actual understanding and implementation of PSA principles for electrical system protection and reliability improvement.

Research Framework

This study focused on selected manufacturing companies located in Laguna, particularly within Calamba Premiere International Park (CPIP). Using a quantitative research design, data were collected through a researcher-developed observation checklist and survey questionnaire administered to technical personnel directly involved in plant operation, maintenance, and electrical compliance. The research employed purposive sampling to select respondents such as facility or plant managers, plant engineers, maintenance supervisors, design engineers, and safety officers. Anchored on the KAP framework, the study examined how knowledge, perceived importance, and actual implementation practices influence the integration of Power System Analysis in industrial facilities. Understanding the knowledge, attitude, and practice toward Power System Analysis provides valuable insights into current industry practices and helps identify opportunities for improving technical competence, regulatory compliance, and engineering decision-making. Ultimately, this study aims to support the development of safer, more reliable, and more sustainable industrial electrical systems and electrical infrastructure management in the manufacturing sector. As shown in Figure 1, the conceptual framework illustrates the relationship between the extent of implementation of PSA and the existing knowledge, attitude, and practice of technical personnel, which ultimately informs the development of management directives for enhanced PSA implementation strategies.

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework of the Study

The study is anchored in the KAP framework, which is widely used in behavioral and organizational research to assess how knowledge influences attitudes, which in turn shape practices. In this research, the framework served as a lens to examine how technical personnel in manufacturing industries understand, perceive, and implement PSA, particularly in terms of its core components: *Short Circuit Analysis*, *Load Flow/Voltage Drop Calculations*, *Protection Coordination*, and *Arc Flash Analysis*, as part of their operational and safety practices. By analyzing the relationship between the current extent of PSA implementation and the KAP of personnel, the study provides a basis for developing management directives aimed at strengthening PSA implementation in manufacturing facilities.

Research Questions

This study examined the implementation of Power System Analysis (PSA) in selected manufacturing companies in Laguna through the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) framework. Guided by the central research question: What is the existing knowledge, attitude, and practice toward Power System Analysis in selected manufacturing industries in Laguna, and how can these inform strategies for improved implementation?

The study addressed the following questions:

1. What is the extent of implementation of PSA and its components among selected manufacturing industries in Laguna, particularly in terms of
 - (a) Short Circuit Analysis,
 - (b) Load Flow Calculation,
 - (c) Protection Coordination Study
 - (d) Arc Flash Analysis
2. What is the existing knowledge, attitude, and practice of technical personnel toward PSA in selected manufacturing industries in Laguna?
3. What management directives can be developed to enhance PSA implementation strategies in selected manufacturing industries in Laguna?

METHODOLOGY

Sampling Method

The study was conducted in CPIP, one of the most established industrial zones in the region that hosts numerous local and multinational manufacturing companies. The park accommodates industries such as electronics, automotive, plastics and molding, food processing, pharmaceuticals, and consumer goods, making it an appropriate setting for examining the implementation of Power System Analysis (PSA) and the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) of technical personnel toward PSA.

A purposive expert sampling approach was used to select the participants of the study. Based on available records, CPIP has 30 major locators, of which 17 are classified as

manufacturing companies. Among these, *Semiconductors and Microelectronics* manufacturing companies were selected as the target population because this sector has the largest representation and operates highly technical and power-sensitive processes where electrical reliability and safety are critical, even minor electrical disturbances may cause production losses, equipment damage, or product defects.

Figure 2. Selection Criteria for Identification of Respondents

From the selection criteria in the figure above, all five Semiconductors and Microelectronics manufacturing companies operating in CPIP were included in the study. From each company, two technical personnel were purposively selected based on their direct involvement in the operation, management, design, or maintenance of electrical systems. These respondents included Facility/Plant Managers, Facility/Plant Engineers, Maintenance Supervisors, Design/Project Engineers, and Safety Officers. In total, ten (10) respondents participated in the study. See the table below for reference.

Table 1. Participants and Total Number of Respondents

PARTICIPANTS	NO. OF RESPONDENTS
Company 1	2
Company 2	2
Company 3	2
Company 4	2
Company 5	2
TOTAL NUMBER OF RESPONDENTS	10

Responses from the two respondents in each company were consolidated and analyzed to represent the participating company as a single unit. This approach minimized isolated individual perspectives and provided a more representative view of the company's knowledge, attitude, and practice toward PSA implementation. Furthermore, by combining and analyzing answers across companies, the study was able to provide an overview of PSA implementation and practices in the sector.

Data Collection Instruments

Two primary instruments were used to collect quantitative data: a researcher-made (1) observation checklist and a (2) survey questionnaire.

1. Observation Checklist

The observation checklist was designed to examine the extent of PSA implementation in the selected manufacturing companies, which is used to answer Research Question 1.

It provided objective documentary and on-site evidence to complement the survey responses and validate the actual implementation of PSA practices, serving as a validation tool for the self-reported survey responses, contributing to the reliability and credibility of the findings of the study.

The checklist consisted of 22 items organized into three categories: (a) General PSA documentation, (b) PSA technical components, and (c) Personnel and Resources. Each item was rated using the scoring system as presented in the table below:

Table 2. Observation Checklist – Scoring System

SCORE	MEANING
0	Not Available (no evidence/implementation)
1	Partially Available (present but incomplete/outdated/not fully implemented)
2	Fully Available (present, updated, and implemented according to standards)

This scoring system allowed the researcher to quantify the level of PSA implementation based on observable and verifiable evidence, such as updated reports, electrical single-line diagrams, protective device settings, and safety documentation. The resulting scores were interpreted using percentage ranges corresponding to varying levels of implementation to provide a clear and consistent basis for analysis.

PSA implementation was classified into different levels of implementation with their corresponding verbal interpretations as shown in the table below. The percentage ranges used unequal, wide-to-narrow intervals based on the practical significance of each implementation level, ensuring that the classification meaningfully represented the extent to which PSA procedures and safety practices were implemented in each facility. This also served as the basis for aligning the levels of implementation with the 4-point Likert scale, providing an objective basis for evaluating PSA practices across facilities.

Table 3. Observation Checklist – Percentage Scoring Interpretation Table

PERCENTAGE SCORING INTERPRETATION FOR OBSERVATION CHECKLIST			
Percentage Range	Level of Implementation	Verbal Equivalent	Meaning
0% – 49%	Very Low Implementation	Poor	PSA is largely absent; components are missing, outdated, or not applied.
50% – 69%	Moderate Implementation	Fair	PSA is partially implemented; some components exist but are incomplete or irregularly applied.

70% – 89%	High Implementation	Good	PSA is implemented in most areas; components are present, updated, and generally applied.
90% – 100%	Very High Implementation	Excellent	PSA is fully implemented; all components are complete, up-to-date, and consistently integrated.

2. Survey Questionnaire

A researcher-developed survey questionnaire was used to measure the knowledge, attitude, and practice (KAP) of technical personnel toward PSA, and assist in answering Research Question 2.

The questionnaire consisted of two parts: (a) Demographic profile of the respondents (position, experience, involvement in electrical operations) and (b) the existing KAP covering the four PSA components: Short Circuit Analysis, Load Flow Analysis, *Protection Coordination Study*, and *Arc Flash Analysis*. Each component was evaluated using seven indicators: *Objectives*, *Procedures*, *Roles*, *Tools*, *Frequency*, *Electrical Safety and Reliability*, and *Regulatory Compliance*. The responses were measured using a 4-point Likert scale: 1 – “Strongly Disagree”, 2 – “Disagree”, 3 – “Agree”, and 4 – “Strongly Agree”. Lower scores imply infrequent or externally dependent practices, while higher scores reflect regular and systematic implementation.

The research instruments were reviewed and validated by two Professional Electrical Engineers (PEE), including a Senior Labor and Employment Officer from DOLE Region IV-A and a subject-matter expert in the field.

Data Analysis

After data collection, the responses from the research instruments were encoded into a spreadsheet to facilitate systematic processing and analysis. Using Descriptive Statistics, including mode, frequency distribution, and percentage, the results were summarized to identify patterns in technical understanding, perceptions, and actual PSA practices. The results were consolidated to identify gaps and the findings served as the basis for developing management directives aimed at strengthening PSA implementation strategies and improving electrical system reliability and safety.

Table 4. Data Analysis Matrix

QUESTION	INSTRUMENT	DATA ANALYSIS
RQ1: What is the extent of implementation of PSA and its components among selected manufacturing industries in Laguna? (a) Short Circuit Analysis,	Primary Data: Researcher-Made Observation Checklist Secondary Data: Existing Journals/Articles	Document Review (PSA Report, training Certificates, software)

(b) Load Flow Calculation (c) Protection Coordination Study (d) Arc Flash Analysis		Descriptive Analysis (Mode, Frequency Distribution, Percentage)
RQ2: What is the existing knowledge, attitude, and practice of technical personnel toward PSA in selected manufacturing industries in Laguna?	Primary Data: Researcher-Made Survey Questionnaire Secondary Data: Existing Journals/Articles	Descriptive Analysis (Mode, Frequency Distribution, Percentage)
RQ3: What management directives can be developed to enhance the PSA implementation strategies in selected manufacturing industries in Laguna?	Result of RQ1+RQ2	n/a

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results and discussion on the implementation of Power System Analysis (PSA) using the KAP framework, examining how PSA is understood, valued, and applied in industrial manufacturing settings. The analysis covered the four PSA components and was evaluated using seven key indicators, while the demographic profile of respondents provided context in interpreting their knowledge, attitude, and practice toward PSA implementation. Findings from the research instruments were interpreted with reference to relevant standards such as National Fire Protection Association (NFPA) and the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC) and were synthesized to develop management directives for enhanced PSA implementation.

Respondents held key engineering and supervisory roles directly involved in electrical system operations and maintenance, including Facilities/Plant Engineers and Design/Project Engineers (each with 30%), Maintenance or Engineering Supervisors (each with 20%), Facilities Managers, and Safety Officers (both with 10%), reflecting the multidisciplinary nature of electrical safety management. This is consistent with NFPA 70E and the Philippine Electrical Engineering Law (RA 7920), which emphasize that electrical hazard assessment and maintenance activities must be handled by qualified personnel.

Enterprise size was also considered as a contextual factor influencing PSA implementation. Results showed that 80% of the respondents were from large-scale manufacturing companies (employing 200 workers or more), while 20% were from medium-sized facilities (100-199 personnel). Larger organizations typically have stronger compliance structures, greater resources, and more established maintenance programs that support PSA implementation, consistent with NFPA 70B (2019), which emphasizes structured maintenance and power system study programs in facilities with complex electrical systems.

Although 60% of respondents had at least 4 years of experience in electrical system operation and maintenance, Haluik (2017) noted that experience alone does not always ensure awareness of electrical risks, reinforcing the need for continuous training. This is particularly relevant since only 40% of respondents had attended PSA-related training, indicating limited structured learning opportunities. In addition, 80% of PSA activities were conducted by external consultants, while only 20% were performed internally, reflecting the specialized nature of PSA, which often requires advanced tools, accurate system modeling, and expert interpretation, as noted by Musti and Ramkhelawan (2012) and Afolabi et al. (2015). However, heavy reliance on outsourcing may also limit internal competency development when knowledge transfer is insufficient, as pointed out by Mendler (2006). Overall, these demographic characteristics provide an important context for interpreting the Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice (KAP) results of the study, as factors such as job role, experience, training exposure, and organizational responsibility influence how PSA knowledge is acquired and translated into practice.

The Extent of Implementation of Power System Analysis (PSA) and its Components

Results in the table below show that PSA implementation varied considerably across the five companies. Only one company achieved *Very High Implementation* (97.73%), indicating almost complete compliance with PSA requirements such as updated short-circuit studies, protection coordination analysis, arc flash assessments, and updated electrical documentation. This company also maintained in-house PSA capability supported by a licensed Professional Electrical Engineer and licensed analytical software, which enabled continuous updating of system studies and proactive identification of system risks.

Table 5. Observation Checklist – Summary of Results

OBSERVATION CHECKLIST RESULTS				
PARTICIPANTS	TOTAL	PERCENTAGE	LEVEL OF IMPLEMENTATION	INTERPRETATION
COMPANY 1	43	97.73%	Very High Implementation	Excellent
COMPANY 2	32	72.73%	High Implementation	Good
COMPANY 3	5	11.36%	Very Low Implementation	Poor
COMPANY 4	30	68.18%	Moderate Implementation	Fair
COMPANY 5	22	50.00%	Moderate Implementation	Fair

In contrast, other companies demonstrated *High* to *Moderate* levels of implementation, while one company exhibited *Very Low Implementation* (11.36%), characterized by minimal PSA documentation and limited awareness of PSA components among technical personnel. In this facility, PSA activities were primarily handled by an external electrical

practitioner serving as a monthly consultant. While this arrangement satisfies minimum legal requirements under RA 7920, it limits internal competence development and proactive system analysis. The findings also revealed that many companies conduct PSA on a project basis, particularly during equipment upgrades or system modifications, rather than as a routine activity. This observation is consistent with previous studies indicating that PSA is often treated as a compliance-driven requirement rather than a continuous reliability tool (Mendler, 2006). When system studies are not regularly updated, opportunities for early fault detection and risk mitigation may be missed.

Overall, the results indicate that PSA implementation is influenced by several factors, including technical capability, management commitment, access to analytical tools, and availability of trained personnel. These findings support the guidance of NFPA 70B (2019), which emphasizes that electrical reliability and safety are best achieved through proactive maintenance practices supported by competent personnel and regularly updated system studies.

The Existing Knowledge, Attitude, and Practice of Technical Personnel Toward PSA

Overall results in the table below showed a consistent pattern of **high Knowledge (4) and Attitude (4) toward PSA but relatively lower levels of Practice (3)**, indicating that although technical personnel understand and value PSA, its implementation remains inconsistent across facilities.

Table 6. Summary of Mode Scores per PSA Component based on KAP Framework

SUMMARY OF MODE SCORES			
PSA COMPONENT	KNOWLEDGE	ATTITUDE	PRACTICE
Short Circuit Analysis	4	4	3
Load Flow Calculation	4	4	4
Protection Coordination Study	3	4	3
Arc Flash Analysis	3	4	4
OVERALL (MODE)	4	4	3

Knowledge

The overall Knowledge mode score was 4 (“Strongly Agree”), indicating a very high level of understanding of PSA concepts, objectives, safety implications, and regulatory requirements. Respondents demonstrated strong awareness of PSA in relation to electrical safety, system reliability, and compliance with regulatory standards such as the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC).

Among the seven indicators, the highest knowledge levels were recorded in *Regulatory Compliance* (90%) and *Electrical Safety and Reliability* (80%). These results indicate that technical personnel clearly recognize PSA as an important requirement for meeting safety

standards and regulatory mandates. Strong knowledge levels were also observed in the indicators *Objectives* and *Roles*, where 50% of respondents strongly agreed, particularly for Short Circuit Analysis and Load Flow Calculation, suggesting that personnel generally understand the purpose of PSA and the role it plays in electrical system safety and reliability. However, lower knowledge levels were observed in the indicators *Procedures*, *Tools*, and *Frequency*, which were dominated by “Agree” responses. Additionally, the *Tools* indicator showed 30% “Strongly Disagree” that they were familiar with PSA software, particularly in relation to Arc Flash and Protection Coordination Studies. These results indicate that although personnel understand the importance of the PSA conceptually, detailed technical familiarity with analytical procedures and specialized software tools remains limited. This pattern is consistent with the operational structure observed in the participating companies, where 80% of PSA studies are conducted by external consultants, limiting the opportunity for internal personnel to perform the analyses themselves.

Across the PSA components, knowledge levels were highest for Short Circuit Analysis and Load Flow Calculation (4). These studies are commonly performed during electrical system design and equipment rating verification, which may explain why respondents demonstrated stronger familiarity. In contrast, Protection Coordination Study and Arc Flash Analysis recorded lower knowledge levels (3), reflecting limited exposure to complex calculations such as time-current coordination and incident energy modelling. This observation aligns with previous studies which indicate that while foundational system studies are widely understood, advanced analyses often require specialized software, training, and expertise that are frequently outsourced (Smith, 2007; Mendler, 2006; Panteli et al., 2013).

Overall, the Knowledge results indicate that technical personnel possess strong conceptual awareness of PSA, particularly in terms of safety and compliance. However, gaps remain in procedural knowledge, analytical tools, and technical execution, suggesting the need for additional training and greater internal participation in PSA activities.

Attitude

The Attitude dimension recorded an overall mode score of 4 (“Strongly Agree”), indicating a very strong positive perception toward PSA implementation. Respondents strongly agreed that PSA plays a crucial role in preventing electrical hazards, improving system reliability, and ensuring regulatory compliance.

Across the indicators, the strongest attitudes were again observed in *Electrical Safety and Reliability* and *Regulatory Compliance*, both having 80% “Strongly Agree” responses. These findings indicate that respondents strongly associate PSA with hazard prevention, worker protection, and adherence to safety regulations. Similarly, the indicators *Objectives* and *Roles* recorded high levels of agreement, with 70% of respondents “Strongly Agree” that PSA is important in electrical system operations. These results reflect a clear recognition of PSA as an essential engineering activity that contributes to

safe and reliable industrial operations. *Frequency* also demonstrated strong support, where 60% of respondents “Strongly Agree” that PSA activities should be conducted regularly, highlighting a strong appreciation of the need for periodic system assessments. However, the indicators *Tools* and *Procedures*, where responses were more evenly distributed between “Agree” and “Strongly Agree”. For instance, 50% “Agree”, and 50% “Strongly Agree” that analytical tools are important for PSA implementation, while 40–50% “Agree” that PSA procedures are necessary but may present practical challenges. These responses suggest that while personnel strongly support PSA in principle, some may perceive difficulties in performing detailed procedures or using analytical tools due to limited training, software availability, or operational constraints. These concerns are consistent with observations made during company visits, where most companies relied on external consultants to conduct PSA studies.

Despite these variations, the Attitude results indicate that technical personnel demonstrate strong support for PSA across all components. This suggests that limitations in PSA implementation are not caused by negative perception, but rather by practical constraints such as limited resources, training opportunities, and access to analytical tools. Similar findings were reported by Panteli et al. (2013) and Haluik (2017), who noted that organizations often maintain strong safety-oriented attitudes toward PSA but face operational barriers that prevent full implementation.

Overall, the Attitude results demonstrate that respondents maintain a strong commitment to electrical safety, reliability, and regulatory compliance, which provides a favorable foundation for improving PSA implementation.

Practice

In contrast to the high Knowledge and Attitude scores, **the overall Practice mode score was 3 (“Agree”)**, indicating that PSA activities are frequently performed but not yet fully systematic or comprehensive.

Among the seven indicators, the strongest Practice results were again observed in *Regulatory Compliance* and *Electrical Safety and Reliability*, each with 70% and 60% Strongly Agree responses, respectively. These results indicate that PSA studies are most commonly performed when they are linked to safety requirements or regulatory compliance obligations. *Roles* also recorded strong practice results, with 50% strongly agreeing that personnel actively participate in PSA-related responsibilities. This suggests that technical personnel are generally aware of their involvement in supporting PSA activities within their organizations. However, weaker implementation patterns were observed in the indicators *Procedures*, *Tools*, and *Frequency*. The indicator *Tools* recorded 40% “Strongly Disagree”, indicating limited access to analytical tools. Similarly, *Frequency* recorded only 20% “Strongly Agree” that PSA studies are conducted regularly, while 20–30% “Disagree”, suggesting that studies may not be consistently updated. These results indicate that although PSA activities are performed, they are often conducted on a compliance basis or during system modifications rather than as routine preventive maintenance practices.

The limited use of analytical tools further reflects the operational structure observed in the study, where 80% of PSA activities are outsourced to external service providers. While outsourcing ensures technical accuracy, it may also limit internal technical capability development and reduce personnel involvement in detailed system analysis. This reactive implementation pattern is consistent with related literatures indicating that many organizations conduct PSA only when required for compliance, system upgrades, or incident investigations rather than as a proactive reliability management practice (Mendler, 2006; Thiele & Beachum, 2009).

Overall, the results reveal a clear gap between understanding and execution, highlighting the need for stronger institutional integration of PSA through structured training, improved access to analytical tools, consistent management support, and regular system study updates.

In terms of company performance, the table below shows that the surveyed companies generally demonstrated high levels of Knowledge and Attitude toward Power System Analysis (PSA), while the Practice dimension varied across organizations, resulting in different overall mode classifications. Companies 1 and 4 obtained an overall mode of 4 (“Strongly Agree”), indicating very high understanding, strong positive attitudes, and PSA practices that were consistently performed as part of routine operations and maintenance. In contrast, Companies 2, 3, and 5 recorded an overall mode of 3 (“Agree”), suggesting that although PSA was recognized and valued, its execution remained present but not fully systematic or comprehensive.

Table 7. Overall Mode Scores per Participant across PSA Components in accordance with the KAP Framework

OVERALL MODE SCORES (ACROSS ALL PSA COMPONENTS)					
FRAMEWORK	PARTICIPANTS				
	COMPANY 1	COMPANY 2	COMPANY 3	COMPANY 4	COMPANY 5
Knowledge	4	3	3	4	3
Attitude	4	4	3	4	4
Practice	4	3	3	4	3
MODE	4	3	3	4	3

Overall, the combined results reinforced the pattern that while technical personnel possessed strong knowledge of PSA and demonstrated positive attitudes toward its importance, actual practice remained variable and constrained by technical, resource, and organizational factors. This misalignment between high Knowledge and Attitude versus moderate Practice highlights a gap between understanding and execution, emphasizing the need for stronger organizational support, targeted training, improved access to analytical tools, and clearer implementation frameworks to bridge the gap between positive attitudes and effective PSA implementation.

Developed Management Directives for Enhanced PSA Implementation Strategies

The results were integrated to develop management directives for enhanced Power System Analysis (PSA) implementation. **While survey results indicated high knowledge and positive attitudes toward PSA, the actual implementation varied across companies, revealing a misalignment between perceived practices and observed on-site evidence and documentation.**

Even though respondents reported high levels of knowledge and favorable attitudes toward PSA, several facilities lacked updated system studies, including short-circuit analysis reports, arc flash assessments, protection coordination studies, and updated electrical diagrams. These findings reinforce previous research showing that many organizations perform PSA reactively rather than proactively, updating system studies only after system failures or modifications occur (Mendler & Osborne, 2006). Outdated PSA studies can significantly increase exposure to electrical hazards and operational failures (Thiele & Beachum, 2009).

Based on the identified gaps between reported KAP and actual PSA implementation, the following **management directives** are proposed to enhance PSA implementation in the surveyed facilities:

- a) **Enhance Technical Training and Capacity Building** to improve personnel capability in conducting PSA studies, use of tools/software, and interpreting analytical results to strengthen internal technical competence (Álvarez-Alvarado et al., 2022; Panteli et al., 2013).
- b) **Integrate PSA into Management Policies and Maintenance Programs**, ensuring defined responsibilities, regular update intervals, and complete documentation aligned with NFPA 70B, PEC, and DOLE requirements. Organizational support plays a key role, as barriers often arise from weak prioritization and inconsistent policies (Garnica & Barriga, 2018; Saeed, 2017).
- c) **Promote Knowledge Sharing and External Collaboration** with external experts, establishing partnerships with industry associations, and training institutions to support accurate system modeling, validated data analysis, and knowledge transfer to internal personnel while maintaining compliance with industry standards (Anderson, 2004; Smith, 2007).
- d) **Improve Resource Allocation and Technological Capability**, investing in PSA software tools and resources, which are essential for accurate system modelling and analysis (Molderink et al., 2010; Romani et al., 2007).
- e) **Institutionalize Continuous Evaluation and Compliance Monitoring**, including periodic audits of PSA documentation, system diagrams, coordination settings, and arc flash labelling to ensure alignment with PEC, DOLE, and NFPA safety standards.
- f) **Improved Compliance with RA 7920 (New Electrical Engineering Law)** by employing sufficient Registered Electrical Engineers (REEs) relevant to

operations, delegating PSA responsibilities to qualified REEs, and supporting electrical technicians in understanding and applying PSA results effectively.

Collectively, these management directives provide a structured approach for improving PSA implementation, strengthening internal technical capacity, and enhancing electrical safety and system reliability in manufacturing facilities.

Conclusions

The following conclusions were drawn based on the major findings of the study and were directly aligned with the research questions and objectives.

- a) The extent of PSA implementation among the selected Semiconductor and Microelectronics manufacturing companies in Laguna remains inconsistent, showing that PSA has not yet been established as a standardized and proactive engineering practice across facilities.
- b) The existing knowledge, attitude, and practice of technical personnel toward PSA show that while technical personnel generally recognize the importance of PSA and demonstrate positive attitudes with adequate foundational knowledge, their ability to effectively practice and implement PSA remains limited and inconsistent due to gaps in procedural understanding, insufficient access to specialized tools, and limited opportunities for hands-on application.
- c) The development of management directives for enhanced PSA implementation strategies addresses the gap between Knowledge and Attitude, and Practice by improving internal capability, strengthening organizational support, and ensuring that PSA activities are consistently updated and well-resourced to promote electrical safety and reliability.

Recommendations

The recommendations were based on the findings and conclusions of the study and aimed to strengthen the implementation of Power System Analysis (PSA) in manufacturing facilities.

The study emphasized the need to **move beyond compliance-driven activities** and **adopt PSA as a proactive engineering management tool** that supports electrical safety, system reliability, operational efficiency, and a well-informed decision-making.

The results highlighted the importance of **strengthening internal technical capability** through regular training, improved access to PSA software and tools, and integration of PSA into routine preventive maintenance programs.

The study also suggested the **development of stronger company policies and regulatory guidelines** aligned with NFPA 70B and the Philippine Electrical Code (PEC) to ensure regular updating of PSA studies and competency standards for personnel involved in system analysis.

In addition, the study promoted **greater awareness and collaboration among industry stakeholders to reinforce PSA as a socially responsible practice** that protects workers, prevents electrical incidents, and supports sustainable industrial operations.

Finally, future researchers are encouraged to **expand the scope of PSA studies** across different sectors, industries, and regions, employ a larger sample size, apply mixed research methods, and examine the relationship between PSA implementation and operational outcomes to further strengthen electrical safety and reliability practices.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

This study adhered to ethical standards to ensure respect, fairness, and integrity throughout the research process. Participation was voluntary, with informed consent obtained from all respondents, who were also informed of their right to withdraw at any time. The researchers protected participants' anonymity, confidentiality, and well-being in compliance with the Data Privacy Act of 2012 (R.A. 10173). The researcher personally administered the instruments to ensure data accuracy, transparency, and integrity, while maintaining honesty and respect. The study was conducted free from conflicts of interest and in accordance with academic standards, including the strict avoidance of plagiarism. Findings were interpreted objectively without bias and used solely for academic purposes, and any use of artificial intelligence tools was disclosed.

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